

Contemporary Marketing and Organizational Performance of selected Foam Manufacturing Firms in Anambra State

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Received: October 19, 2023; Accepted: April 1, 2024 ; Published: April 22, 2024.

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11021880

Abstract: This study looked at how modern marketing affected the organizational performance of a few chosen Anambra State foam manufacturing companies. The study's specific goal was to ascertain how foam manufacturing companies in Anambra State, Nigeria performed organizationally in relation to transaction, interactive, database, and e-marketing marketing strategies. The 1647 employees of the eight chosen foam manufacturing companies in Anambra State made up the study's population. The Borg and Gall (1967) statistical formula was utilized to ascertain the sample size of 322. Both Pearson correlation analysis and descriptive statistics were used to analyze the obtained data. The multiple regression analysis method was used to test the proposed hypotheses. According to the study, transaction marketing significantly improves organizational performance. Interactive marketing has a significant positive effect on organizational performance in foam manufacturing firms in the Anambra State Nigeria. Database marketing has a significant positive effect on organizational performance in foam manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria. E-marketing has significant positive effect on organizational performance in foam manufacturing firms in the Anambra State Nigeria. The study concludes that contemporary marketing have a significant positive effect on organizational performance in foam manufacturing firms in Anambra, State. The study recommended that management of these firms should pay adequate attention to the implementation of firms contemporary marketing strategy and customer centered programs to achieve profitability and performance.

Keywords: *Transaction marketing, Interactive marketing, Database marketing, E-marketing and Organizational Performance.*

Introduction

Since its inception during the First and Second World Wars, marketing has undergone tremendous transformation as unique economic and management

phenomena. Marketing used to be primarily concerned with gaining new clients; now days, it also focuses on keeping existing ones. The question of whether conventional marketing concepts—which were created in

the drastically different environment of the 1950s and 1960s—are still relevant and appropriate for SMEs emerges in light of the nature and degree of change that is visible in marketing operations.

In other words, the traditional marketing theories were created specifically for consumer markets that were quite different from the crowded, fiercely competitive marketplaces of the twenty-first century. A modern marketing strategy must serve as the operational cornerstone for SMEs if they are to achieve comprehensive business success. SMEs have taken into account the necessity of creating methods that facilitate market comprehension, particularly when interacting with clients and rivals. Financial limitations, management expertise, leadership qualities, marketing, planning, and education were all recognized by Akindoju (2016) as being crucial factors in determining whether SMEs succeed or fail. However, the study's only focus was on how marketing contributed to success or failure.

According to Dzisi and Ofosu (2014), using modern marketing techniques is crucial for promoting the success and expansion of SMEs. SMEs may not have the necessary modern marketing abilities and tactics (Kozan & Akdeniz, 2014, for example). This is clear from the justifications that managers frequently offer for the poor

market conditions: (a) inadequate product development; (b) insufficient marketing strategies; (c) inadequate market knowledge; and (d) incomplete product commercialization as contributing factors to poor market positioning (Hacioglu, Eren, Eren, & Celikkan, 2012). Small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) are thought to have contributed to over 90% of firms globally and generated over 50% of jobs. Nigeria, a developing country, has seen SMEs have a significant impact on economic activity.

A growing number of SMEs in an economy has provided a crucial area of emphasis for governments, scholars, and other participants due to its vivid influences towards job creation, improvement of GDP and export incomes, and consequent decrease in unemployment and the social, political, and economic quagmire associated with an economy. Scholars such as Mohamad, Mustapa, and Razak, (2021), Baporikar, Nambira, and Gomxos, (2016), and SMEDAN and NBS (2013) noted the magnificent significance of SMEs.

However, Gwadabe and Amirah (2017) discovered that the lack of business experience is the reason for Nigeria's economy's continued downturn. Similarly, researchers such as SMEDAN in Aminu, 2016; Gwadabe and Amirah, 2017)

expressed dissatisfaction with the high death rate and low performance of SMEs in Nigeria. This is demonstrated by Aminu et al. (2015), who found that almost 80% of SMEs in Nigeria fail before reaching their fifth anniversary. He affirmed that access to capital is not the only factor that may ensure the growth and optimal performance of SMEs in Nigeria; in order to boost performance, SMEs must be encouraged to adopt modern marketing (CM).

Many studies have examined the effects of many business orientations, but they have examined each orientation separately or in conjunction with a few others. The relationship between the success of SMEs and modern marketing has not received much attention in the literature. There is also a dearth of research on the optimal alignment, deployment, and effect of modern marketing strategy on the success of SMEs. Even though there is a substantial body of empirical study on how modern marketing affects SMEs' performance, most of it focused on large companies or was carried out in developed nations (Haugland, Myrtveit, & Nygaard, 2007; Hult, Hurley, & Knight, 2004).

Consequently, the scarcity of research on manufacturing companies in developing nations such as Nigeria limits the understanding and application of strategic orientations (Mu & Di Benedetto, 2011). In

order to understand modern marketing practice and the performance of SMEs in light of the aforementioned research gaps, the purpose of this study is to align the framework that has been developed by Coviello et al. (2001) and further conceptualized by Brodie et al. (2008). The framework is based upon five marketing approaches: transaction marketing, database marketing, e-marketing, interaction marketing, and network marketing.

Research Methods

Small-scale, medium-scale, large-scale, and micro/cottage industries are the four (4) scales into which Nigerian business organizations are divided. Nevertheless, only small and medium-sized businesses are covered in this study. According to the NBS & SMEDAN (2013) report, Nigeria has over 72,838 registered SMEs. Since the sector was essential to both societal and economic growth and development worldwide, SMEs attracted a great deal of attention (Nwoye, Obiorah, & Ekesiobi, 2015)..

On the other hand, because the government relies too heavily on oil for its principal source of income, the SMEs sector has been disregarded by the government for a long time. Due to this, SMEs performed poorly, and only a small percentage of them made it through the fiercely competitive business

climate. This is a significant problem that should worry all parties involved (Osinbajo, 2015a). The current government restates its resolve to bring the industry back to life and turn it into a sustainable economy. Consequently, in light of this pledge, the availability of CM will enhance the performance of Nigeria's SMEs industry.

The literature lacks a precise definition of SME. The idea changes with time and throughout organizations (World Bank, 2013). In Nigeria, different agencies and organizations have defined SME differently over time, but conventional metrics such as fixed assets, gross output, and workforce size are always included in the definitions. Accordingly, the definition of SMEs is determined by the total assets in Nigerian Naira (NGN), excluding land and buildings, and the number of employees (NBS & SMEDAN, 2013; Oboreh et al., 2013; Ogechukwu, 2011)

According to Sorooshian et al. (2016), there is a lack of agreement on the meaning, which leads to misunderstandings and clearly restricts the possibility of an overview and comparability of works in the field. Performance metrics, performance evaluation, performance assessment, and firm performance, for example, are terms that can be used interchangeably. According to a dictionary of management sciences, performance is defined as the completion of

a work as assessed against predetermined, established standards for cost, speed, accuracy, and completeness (Al-Dhaafri et al., 2016; Sorooshian et al., 2016). SME performance could be assessed using a variety of criteria or indicators, including financial and non-financial measurements, according to Hussain, Ismail, and Shah (2015).

Return on investment, profitability, return on assets, market share, and sales growth are a few examples of financial metrics that can be used to assess it. Non-financial metrics include competitiveness, customer satisfaction, staff satisfaction, service quality, and innovation. Moreover, the performance of SMEs can be understood as the way the company provides value to its clients and stakeholders, demonstrating how successfully the management allocates the company's resources (Penrose, 1959). A SMEs is considered to be operating effectively when it has utilized its resources to meet its overall goals (Aminu & Mahmood, 2016; Sorooshian et al., 2016).

Performance can be understood as the result of a company's resource commitment combined with its key performance indicators and the achievement of its intended objectives, based on the concepts and definitions mentioned above (Aminu & Mahmood, 2016; Chen et al., 2016). In summary, the significance of small and

medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) cannot be overstated, given their enormous contributions to the economy in the areas of innovation, regional development, and social cohesion. These factors ultimately contribute to the GDP and job possibilities (Bouri et al., 2011).

Contemporary Marketing

Contemporary marketing theory is “a recent strong conceptualisation of marketing that replicates and classifies existing and emergent 'best practice' in the marketplace” O’Driscoll (2006). Although it might be argued that few theories in the social sciences can be defined so clinically, some earlier arguments linger on in the contemporary marketing field. The academic-practitioners divide arguments are “hoary, repetitive and infinite” (Levy, 2002). Modern practitioners concerned more with making accurate resolutions at a specific point in time than the managerial consequences of scientifically derived and manipulated research (Coviello & Joseph, 2012).

The underline distinctions between the dimensions of the CM variables succinctly are; *Transactional marketing*: manages the marketing mix elements to attract and satisfy customers. *Database marketing*: using technology-based techniques and tools to create and retain loyal customers. *E-*

marketing: presenting product and brand to attract potential and current customers through the use of internet and other technological devices. *Interaction marketing*: creating an interpersonal relationship to build cooperative interaction between buyers and sellers for a shared benefit; and *Network marketing*: establishing an interorganisational relationship to allow for coordination of activities between organizations for mutual benefit and resource exchange.

Contemporary Marketing and SMEs Performance

Limited studies have looked into the effect of contemporary marketing and organizational performance, especially in the emerging economy (Adeniyi, 2011; Coviello & Joseph, 2012; Iyalla, 2015). However, most of the studies on CM are on a one-dimensional approach which explores one aspect of CM dimension with firm performance (Ibojo, 2016; Kuboye & Ogunlobi, 2013). Equally, the majority of the studies focus more on marketing strategies and firm’s performance, and marketing orientation with firm performance (Deshpande et al., 2013; Hussain et al., 2015). However, despite increased attention in the literature on newer forms of practice, and the fact that they are all implemented by the firms in Coviello &

Joseph (2012) sample, these appear to have no impact directly on either influencing performance or to enhance the effect of transaction marketing and interaction marketing. Brodie, Winklhofer, Coviello, and Johnston (2007) provided a broader examination across industries. Their study was a follow-up to the UK and New Zealand research from Coviello, Brodie, Brookes, and Palma (2003) and used data from two US samples collected in 2002 and 2005. The study findings show that the penetration of e-marketing was significant, with over two-thirds of US firms having medium or high levels of e-marketing application (Brodie et al., 2007). The findings also show the adoption of e-marketing as positively associated with improved acquisition performance, which, in turn, influences performance. Additionally, the implementation of e-marketing increases the effectiveness and efficiency of database marketing and network marketing practices. The success of e-marketing, therefore, comes from the support and enhancement of existing marketing practices, rather than e-marketing transforming the business model. Thus, the adoption of e-marketing is shown to largely be a consequence of its integration with other marketing practices.

According to Haghghinasab, Sattari, Ebrahimi and Roghanian, (2013) performance can be measured based on growth, market share and profitability. The higher the indices the greater the performance of the business and vice versa. Ardjouman and Asma (2015) further defined performance in terms of output such as profitability or quantified objectives. This means that performance of SMEs has to do with both behaviour and results. This explanation covers achievements of anticipated levels as well as objective review and setting. When the behaviour of management is right, then the anticipated levels of output would be achieved and vice versa for failure. When behaviours of management towards marketing strategies are geared on a right direction, then this positively affect the performance of SMEs. Some strategies which could affect performance of businesses are the product quality, marketing communication and relationship marketing.

Therefore, in line with the above arguments from prior studies, this study hypostasizes that:

***H1.** There is a significant relationship between transaction marketing and sales growth of small and medium enterprise*

H2. There is a significant relationship between interaction marketing and sales growth of small and medium enterprise

H3. There is a significant relationship between database marketing and sales growth of small and medium enterprise

H4. There is a significant relationship between e-marketing and sales growth of small and medium enterprise

Theoretical Framework

Resource-Based View

The theory of resource-based view can be used to build competitiveness for strategic marketing. This theory suggests that the competitive advantage lies in the resources that a company can access and use, not in the capacity to control the environment (Campbell, 2004). The theory states that firms have three types of resources namely; tangible resources, intangible resources, and organizational capabilities. Tangible resources include financial, physical, technological and organizational assets and thus are easily identified. Conversely intangible resources are more complex to identify and therefore hard to imitate. They include strategies that an organization adopts over time and ends to better-quality performance (Barney, Caroline, & David, 2002). Lastly, organizational capabilities are skills and capabilities which an organization combines to transform tangible and

intangible resources into outputs, for example, outstanding customer service (Dess, Lumpkin, & Eisner, 2007). It ensures that organizations are well endowed with an array of resources in the form of assets, know-how, processes, and substitutes that offer a competitive advantage to the company. The theory views CM as strategic capability and resource of the firm that can influence performance output (Pratono & Mahmood, 2015). CM is considered as firm's inclination to create and deliver superior value to its customers in the context of the new order of relationship marketing.

Conceptual Framework

Owing to the inconsistencies found in the previous studies, this work developed a research framework to determine the relationship between CM and SMEs performance in Nigeria. The framework has CM as the independent variable and operationalised with (transaction, interaction, database, and electronic marketing), SMEs performance as the dependent variable was measured with sales growth. The study focuses on SME's performance which eventually leads to profitability and success of a firm. CM represents the firm's valuable, rare, inimitable and non-substitutable (VRIN) resource as signified by the resource-based

view (RBV) theory. The proposition of the

framework is that CM has implications on the performance of SMEs.

Source; Researchers conceptual framework

Research Design

The research method adopted in this study is the descriptive survey method. Descriptive survey method is probably the best method available to a researcher who is interested in collecting original data for describing a

population too large to be observed directly.

Population of the Study

The population of the study is the entire staff of the selected foam manufacturing firms in the Anambra State. Therefore, the population of the study is (1647) as at September, 2023 as extracted from each of the firms’ personnel unit.

Table 1 Population of the Selected Foam, Manufacturing Firms.

S/n	Name of foam, Firms	Location	Population
1.	D Syndivel Foam Firms Ltd	Awka	249
2.	Rima Foam Firms Ltd	Onitsha	109
3.	Elyfoam Firms Ltd	Nkpor	125
4.	Continental Foam Firms Ltd	Nnewi	164
5.	Winco Foam Firms Ltd	Awka	117
6.	Vital Foam Firms Ltd.	Onitsha	156
7.	Muoka Foam Firms Ltd, Ltd	Onitsha	117
8.	Daco Foam, Firms Ltd,	Enugu	310
Total			1647

Source: Extracted from each of the companies Personnel Department as at May, 2023.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The finite population sample size for this study was determined using statistical formula quoted by Okeke (2005):

$$n = N / [1 + N (e)^2]$$

Where:

n = Sample size

N = Total population

e = Tolerable error at 5%

1 = Constant

Therefore:

$$n = 1647/[1+1647 (0.05)^2]$$

$$n = 1647/[1+(1647 \times 0.0025)]$$

$$n = 1647/5.12$$

$$n = 322$$

Method of Data Analysis

The tools used in analyzing the data collected include descriptive statistics and Pearson correlation analysis. The study

also employed Multiple Regression Analysis (MRA) method to determine the effect of leadership style on organizational performance.

Research Findings and Discussion

Results of the Regression Analysis

Multiple regression analysis was employed to determine the effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The essence is to ascertain the

effect of contemporary marketing and organizational performance. The results are presented in tables 2 and 3.

Test of Hypotheses

Here, the four hypotheses formulated earlier in this study were tested using the t-statistics and probability from the

coefficient result of the multiple regression analysis. The results are presented the table 4 below

Table 2 Model Summary of Regression Result

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.174 ^a	.530	.617	3.197	1.745

a. Predictors: (Constant), *Transaction Marketing, Interaction Marketing, Database marketing, E- marketing*

b. Dependent Variable: Organizational Performance

Table 2 above indicates that R^2 which measures the strength of the effect of independent variable on the dependent variable have the value of 0.530. This implies that 53.0% of the variation in organizational performance is explained by variations in reward variables (Autocratic leadership style, Laissez-faire leadership style

Transformational leadership style, and Democratic leadership). This was supported by adjusted R^2 of 61.7%. The Durbin-Watson statistics was employed to check for autocorrelation in the model. Durbin-Watson statistics of 1.742 show that the variables in the model are not auto-correlated and are therefore, reliable for predications

Table 3: ANOVA Result

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	112.562	5	22.512	72.203	.004 ^a
	Residual	3587.511	351	10.221		
	Total	3700.073	356			

a. Predictors: (Constant), *Transaction Marketing, Interaction Marketing, Database marketing, E-marketing.*

b. Dependent Variable: Organizational Performance

The F-test is applied to check the overall significance of the model. The F-statistic is instrumental in verifying the overall significance of an estimated model. The f-statistics value of 72.203 in table 3 above with probability value of 0.004 shows that the independent variables has significant effect on dependent variable. This shows

that Predictors: (Constant), Transaction Marketing, Interaction Marketing, Database marketing, and E-marketing can collectively explain the variations in organizational performance. This shows that contemporary marketing has a significant positive effect on organizational performance.

Table 4 Coefficients of the Regression Result

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	22.159	1.757		12.612	.000
	Transaction Marketing	1.040	.040	.054	2.003	.007
	Interaction Marketing	.056	.042	.071	2.340	.001
	Database marketing	1.108	.042	.140	3.580	.000
	E-marketing	.083	.043	.102	2.924	.005

a. Dependent Variable: Organizational Performance

Discussion

Test of Hypothesis One

Ho: Transaction Marketing has no significant positive effects on organizational performance in foam manufacturing firms in the Anambra State, Nigeria.

Hi: Transaction Marketing has a significant positive effect on organizational performance of foam manufacturing firms in the Anambra State, Nigeria.

Table 4 above indicates that transaction marketing recorded a t-statistics value of 2.340 with a probability value of 0.001 which is statistically significant at 5% level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. This implies that transaction marketing has a significant positive effect on organizational performance.

Test of Hypothesis Two

Ho: Interaction Marketing has no significant positive influence on organizational performance of foam manufacturing firms in the Anambra State Nigeria.

Ho_i: Interaction Marketing has a significant positive influence on organizational performance of foam manufacturing firms in the Anambra

State Nigeria.

Interaction Marketing recorded a t-statistics value of 2.003 with an alpha value of 0.007. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. This implies that interaction marketing has a significant positive effect on organizational performance.

Test of Hypothesis Three

Ho: Database marketing has no significant effects on organizational performance of foam manufacturing firms in the Anambra State Nigeria

Hi: Database marketing has a significant positive effect on organizational performance of foam manufacturing firms in the Anambra State Nigeria

Database marketing recorded a t-statistics value of 3.580 with a

probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant at 5% level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. It is therefore concluded that Database marketing has a significant positive effects on organizational performance of foam manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria

Test of Hypothesis Four

Ho: E-marketing has no significant effects on organizational performance of foam manufacturing firms in the Anambra State Nigeria.

Hi: E-marketing has no significant effects on organizational performance of foam manufacturing firms in the Anambra State Nigeria.

E-marketing has a t-statistics value of 2.924 with a probability value of 0.005 which is statistically significant at 5% level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. It is therefore concluded E-marketing has a significant positive effect on organizational performance

Summary of Findings

This work examined the effect of contemporary marketing on organizational performance in foam manufacturing firms in Anambra State, Nigeria. The data generated

were analyzed using multiple regression analysis and the following were discovered that.

1. Transaction marketing has a significant positive effect on organizational performance. Transaction marketing recorded a t-statistics value of 2.340 with

a probability value of 0.001 which is statistically significant at 5% level of significance

2. Interaction marketing has a significant

positive effect on organizational performance in foam manufacturing firms in the Anambra State Nigeria. Interaction marketing recorded a t-statistics value of 2.003 with an alpha value of 0.007.

3. Database marketing has a significant positive effect on organizational performance in foam manufacturing firms in Anambra State Nigeria. Database marketing

recorded a t-statistics value of 3.580 with a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant at 5% level.

4. E-marketing has significant positive effect on organizational performance in foam manufacturing firms in the Anambra State Nigeria. E-marketing has a t-statistics value of 2.924 with a probability value of 0.005 which is statistically significant at 5% level

Conclusion

This work examined effect of contemporary marketing on organizational performance using form manufacturing firms in Anabaria State. From the analysis it was discovered transaction marketing has a significant positive effect on organizational performance. Interactive marketing has a significant positive effect on organizational performance in foam manufacturing firms. Database marketing has significant positive effect on

organizational performance in foam manufacturing firms in the Anambra State Nigeria. E-marketing has a significant positive effect on organizational performance. Therefore, the study concludes that contemporary marketing has a significant positive effect on organizational performance in foam manufacturing firms in Anambra State

Recommendations

The management of these firms should pay adequate attention to the implementation of contemporary marketing strategy to achieve organizational performance.

1. Form manufacturing firms should adopt transaction marketing to trigger unprecedented enterprises

developed, growth and expansion.

2. Effective implementation of interactive marketing has the potentials of expanding market share and sustains organizations in the face of stiff competition in meeting their desired performance.
3. The management of these firms

should take effective measures in ensuring that database marketing is practiced in organization to enhance performance.

4. Management should adopt the use of E-marketing to compete favorably in the form markets.

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